
**Application of Acidic [BTEAC][OX.2H₂O] Deep Eutectic Solvent/Catalyst;
Green Solvent for Synthesis of Hydrazone Schiff Bases From 2-acetyl-1-
naphthol**

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Abstract:

Considering enormous applications of hydrazone schiff bases in various fields, a series of 1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-substituted-benzoylhydrazone (H₂L¹-H₂L⁴) schiff bases were synthesized using green, environmentally benign acidic benzyltriethylammoniumchloride [BTEAC] deep eutectic solvents. From the study of optimized reaction conditions, [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES gives excellent reaction yield within reduced time. Catalytic property of DES was further compared with conventional reflux method; obviously [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES proves to be good solvent as well as catalyst along with possessing recoverable and reuse capability.

Keywords: *Green Solvent, Deep Eutectic Solvent, Hydrazone Schiff Bases, Environment Benign Method.*

Introduction:

Acyl hydrazones are special type of Schiff bases, possessing interlinked nitrogen atoms attached to carbonyl group (R₁R₂C=NNHCOR₃). Introducing a >C=O group into the hydrazide portion enhances the electron delocalization of the hydrazone, which is an attractive functional group in synthesis of coordination complexes [1] and also in heterocyclic synthesis [2]. Presence of hydrazone functional group and incorporation of various biologically active groups increases biological activity in hydrazone schiff bases. Several derivatives of hydrazone schiff bases reported in literature exhibits promising antiviral, anti-fungal, antibacterial, anti-tubercular, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant etc [3]. Hydrazone Schiff bases are conventionally synthesized in organic solvents such as ethanol, methanol, dimethyl sulfoxide, dimethylformamide, etc., using catalysts like acetic acid, concentrated hydrochloric acid,

concentrated sulfuric acid, etc. [4]. However, challenges such as excessive solvent and catalyst usage, long reaction times, high temperatures, and low yields persist in conventional synthesis [5]. Additionally, organic solvents pose toxicity issues, and catalysts are difficult to reuse and recover. Therefore, a new set of green condition is necessary to mitigate these drawbacks of the conventional approach.

In search of green and environmentally benign procedures 'Deep eutectic solvents '(DES), a green and new generation solvent satisfy both catalyst as well as solvent properties in numerous organic transformations [6]. It was first introduced by Abbott's group in 2003 [7], represent a new class of nonaqueous solvents with properties similar to ionic liquids (ILs). Aim of present work is compare conventional method of synthesis of hydrazone schiff bases from our previous work [8-10] using acidic BTEAC, DESs as

greener solvent under optimized condition. [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES, proves to be a remarkable potential solvent/catalyst to increase yield of product within short time.

Experimental:

Material and Methods:

Starting materials are synthesized from analytical grade (AR) chemicals and solvents. They are used without purification and procured from S. D. Fine. Synthesis of all hydrazone schiff bases were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) pre-coated silica gel plates and visualising using UV chamber. Melting points were determined by the open capillary method, using electrical melting point apparatus. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr disc in the range of 4000-350 cm⁻¹. ¹H-NMR are recorded in DMSO-d⁶ solvent on Bruker 400MHz spectrophotometer, using TMS as internal standard. 2-acetyl-1-naphthol [11] and substituted benzohydrazides are synthesized from literature methods [12].

Preparation of deep eutectic solvents (DESs):

Acidic BTEAC, DESs were synthesized by method given in literature [13]. Benzyltriethylammoniumchloride [BTEAC] (1 mmol) and acid (1 mmol) were added into a round bottom flask. The mixture was heated at 100 °C and stirred for 15 min for malonic acid and 1 h for oxalic,

citric acid and benzoic acids, until a clear, colourless liquid was obtained.

General procedure for the synthesis of 1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-substituted benzohydrazone (H₂L¹, H₂L², H₂L³ & H₂L⁴):

Conventional method:

To a hot ethanolic solution (15ml) of substituted benzoylhydrazide (0.01mol), hot ethanolic solution (15ml) of 2-acetyl-1-naphthol (0.01mol) was added with continuous stirring in round bottom flask and reaction mixture was heated under reflux on water bath for 3-4 hr. After cooling, the coloured solid obtained was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried under vacume of CaCl₂. It was finally recrystallized from DMF- ethanol mixture (1:4 v/v).

Using DES:

A mixture of benzoyl hydrazines (0.1 mmol) and 2-acetyl-1-naphthol (0.1 mmol) and 1.5 ml DES was stirred at optimized temperature 80 °C for an appropriate time (Scheme 1). The reaction was monitored by TLC (ethylacetate:hexane). After completion of reaction, the mixture was diluted to water, filtered and dried to get product and recrystallized from 1:1 (v/v) DMF/ethanol. The DES could be recovered by vaporization of its aqueous solution under vacuum to furnish the used DES for the next reaction run.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of benzohydrazone schiff bases in [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES

Table 1. Analytical data of Schiff bases H_2L^1 - H_2L^4

Hydrazone Schiff base	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight	Colour	Melting point	Elemental Analysis found (calculated)			
					C%	H%	N%	Cl%
H_2L^1	$C_{19}H_{15}ClN_2O_2$	338.79	Lemon Yellow	211	67.28 (67.36)	4.18 (4.46)	7.98 (8.27)	10.49 (10.46)
H_2L^2	$C_{19}H_{15}ClN_2O_2$	338.79	Golden Yellow	202	67.01 (67.36)	3.88 (4.46)	8.08 (8.27)	10.00 (10.46)
H_2L^3	$C_{19}H_{14}Cl_2N_2O_2$	373.23	Yellow	170	61.16 (61.14)	3.42 (3.78)	7.21 (7.51)	18.43 (19.00)
H_2L^4	$C_{19}H_{15}IN_2O_2$	430.24	Pale Yellow	173	52.78 (53.04)	3.04 (3.51)	6.31 (6.51)	—

1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-2-chlorobenzoylhydrazone (H_2L^1):

FT-IR (KBr, 4000–400 cm^{-1}): ν (N-H) 3190, ν (O-H) 2995, ν (C=O) 1637, ν (C=N) 1589 [14].

1H -NMR (400MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 14.74, (1H, S, phenolic OH); δ 11.62, (1H, S, imino NH); δ 2.52, (3H, S, methyl); δ 8.29, (1H, d, naphthyl); δ 7.79, (1H, d, phenyl); δ 7.45-7.62 ppm, (5H, m, naphthyl); δ 7.25-7.50 ppm, (3H, m, phenyl) [15].

1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-4-chlorobenzoylhydrazone (H_2L^2):

FT-IR (KBr, 4000–400 cm^{-1}): ν (N-H) 3211, ν (O-H) 3005, ν (C=O) 1633, ν (C=N) 1593.

1H -NMR (400MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 14.82, (1H, S, phenolic OH); δ 11.34, (1H, S, imino NH); δ 2.55, (3H, S, methyl); δ 8.28, (1H, d, naphthyl); δ 7.40-7.85 ppm, (5H, m, naphthyl); δ 7.54-7.99 ppm, (4H, m, phenyl)

1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-2,4-chlorobenzoylhydrazone (H_2L^3):

FT-IR (KBr, 4000–400 cm^{-1}): ν (N-H) 3207, ν (O-H) 2995, ν (C=O) 1629, ν (C=N) 1587.

1H -NMR (400MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 14.75, (1H, S, phenolic OH); δ 11.73, (1H, S, imino NH); δ 2.51, (3H, S, methyl); δ 8.36, (1H, d, naphthyl); δ 7.81, (1H, d, phenyl); δ 7.66, (1H, S, phenyl); δ 7.58-7.72, (5H, m, naphthyl)

1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-2-iodobenzoylhydrazone (H_2L^4):

FT-IR (KBr, 4000–400 cm^{-1}): ν (N-H) 3194, ν (O-H) 2997, ν (C=O) 1654, ν (C=N) 1583.

1H -NMR (400MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ 14.85, (1H, S, phenolic OH); δ 11.68, (1H, S, imino NH); δ 2.51, (3H, S, methyl); δ 8.36, (1H, d, naphthyl); δ 7.98, (1H, d, naphthyl); δ 7.88-7.89, (2H, dd, phenyl); δ 7.72 (1H, d, naphthyl); δ 7.15-7.30, (4H, m, aromatic)

Results and Discussion:

We begin our study with synthesis of 1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-2-chlorobenzoylhydrazone (H_2L^1); prepared from 2-acetyl-1-naphthol and 2-chlorobenzoylhydrazide as model reaction in [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES as solvent as well as catalyst. To explore and optimise reaction conditions, various catalyst mol% of [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES at different temperature was studied (table 2, entry 1-7). As shown in Table 2, desired product was obtained with good yield (92%) using 20 mol% of [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES at 80°C within least time (table 2, entry 7). Result shows that, higher the reaction temperature, more efficiently reaction could proceed in short time. Now same reaction condition was applied using [BTEAC][malonic acid], [BTEAC][citric acid] and [BTEAC][Benzoic acid] DESs, under optimum temperature; 80°C. Results reveals that [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES was played better role as catalyst as well as solvent than others (table 2, entry 8-10).

Table 2. Effect of reaction time, temperature and catalyst mol% and yield on synthesis of 1-(1-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)ethanone-2-chlorobenzoylhydrazone (H_2L^1)

Entry	DES/Solvent	Catalyst mol%	Temp.(° C)	Time (min)	Yield
1	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O]	5	70	50	50
2	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O]	5	75	42	65
3	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O]	5	80	25	78
4	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O]	5	85	22	76
5	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O]	10	80	20	82
6	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O]	15	80	18	88
7	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O]	20	80	10	92
8	[BTEAC][malonic acid]	20	80	25	80
9	[BTEAC][citric acid]	20	80	40	72
10	[BTEAC][Benzoic acid]	20	80	45	68
11	Ethanol/CH ₃ COOH	-	70-80	240	65
12	Methanol/CH ₃ COOH	-	70-80	245	60

Model reaction was then compared with conventional reaction conditions (table 2, entry 11-12). The conventional method showed that synthesis of schiff bases also delivered the expected product but with poor yield and these reports still suffered intrinsic drawbacks such as the requirement of long

reaction time and volatile organic solvent. All synthesized schiff bases are stable to room temperature, non-hygroscopic and insoluble in water (table 1). IR and ¹H-NMR data matches with the structure of hydrazone schiff bases.

Table 3. Comparison of % yield and time of hydrazone Schiff's bases (H_2L^1 - H_2L^4) in conventional and [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES

Hydrazone schiff bases	R ₁	R ₂	Conventional solvent Ethanol(CH ₃ COOH) %yield (time)	[BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H ₂ O] DES %yield (time)
H_2L^1	-Cl	-H	65 (240 min)	90 (10 min)
H_2L^2	-H	-Cl	60 (200 min)	92 (10 min)
H_2L^3	-Cl	-Cl	68 (260 min)	85 (15 min)
H_2L^4	-I	-H	62 (300 min)	82 (18 min)

Applicability of [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES was further investigated for synthesis of H₂L² - H₂L⁴ hydrazone schiff bases and also compared with conventional method. All schiff bases are obtained in good isolated yield than in conventional solvent within minimum time (table 3, entry 1-4). We have also studied recyclability of DES 1 under the optimized conditions. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was poured in ice cold water and the product was filtered. The [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] was recovered by simply evaporating water from the reaction mass after filtration of the solid product. The Deep Eutectic Solvent recovered from the previous run was reused for the next reaction without further purification [16]. This procedure was repeated several times, and the catalytic activity of DES was slightly changed after 4th cycle.

Conclusion:

The current work was featured by outstanding performance of [BTEAC][oxalic acid.2H₂O] DES in synthesis of hydrazone schiff bases. The reaction was compared with conventional method using ethanol, gives excellent yield within short time. Simple method of preparation of DES, high stability, remarkable potential to act as solvent as well as catalyst and easy recover ability, creates a new hope in organic transformations to replace dangerous volatile solvents.

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